

β -Substituted Hydrazones of Acetoacetarylamides

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Semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones, benzoylhydrazones, and salicylhydrazones of acetoacetarylamides have been prepared to explore various aspects of the condensation reaction and products.

Arylamides of acetoacetic acid have been extensively and intensively studied with respect to their methylene group activity. But excepting some isolated attempts for the preparation of derivatives from acetoacetic ester and its derivatives and acetoacetanilide by replacing the carbonyl group, a systematic study on the acetoacetarylamide derivatives, formed by the condensation of substituted hydrazines with the carbonyl group, seems meagre.

Do¹ and Do and Dutt² prepared semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones of acetoacetic ester, derivatives of acetoacetic ester, benzoylacetic ester, and diacetosuccinic ester. They studied the cyclisation behaviour of these products, but did not interpret their results on stereoisomeric possibilities.

With this background, it appeared worthwhile to prepare semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones, benzoylhydrazones, and salicylhydrazones of acetoacetarylamides in order to study them from five different aspects, viz., (i) mechanism of formation of substituted hydrazones in relation to their possible stereoisomers, (ii) cyclisation of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones, (iii) absorption spectra in UV region, (iv) chelation capacity, and (v) biological properties.

The present communication deals with the preparation of several β -substituted hydrazones of a number of acetoacetarylamides. The general reaction takes place as shown below.

where R = aryl ; R' = -CONH₂, -CSNH₂, -COPh, -COC₆H₄(OH).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Acetoacetanilide Semicarbazone.—Acetoacetanilide (17.7 g.), dissolved in ethanol (40 ml) in a r.b. flask (500 ml), was treated with an aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydro-

1. *This Journal*, 1926, 3, 30.
2. *Ibid.*, 1928, 5, 459; 1930, 7, 473.

chloride (11.1g. in 100ml) and sodium acetate (10g.). After the operation, the solution was stirred well and kept for a few minutes, when a white precipitate of the semicarbazone separated. Stirring was continued occasionally for 1 hr. and finally the content of the flask was diluted to about 400 ml with water. The product was filtered, washed with water, and dried at the room temperature under vacuum. On recrystallisation of the dried product from aqueous ethanol, white short needles were obtained; m.p. 160°, yield 70%.

Acetoacetanilide Thiosemicarbazone.—Acetoacetanilide (17.7 g.) dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol, was mixed with hot aqueous solution (100 ml) of thiosemicarbazide (10g.) and a few drops of HCl (dil.) in a conical flask (250 ml). The mixture was stirred and allowed to stand for 5-6 hr., when the white crystalline thiosemicarbazone separated. The product was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 161°, yield 80%.

Acetoacetanilide Benzoylhydrazone.—Acetoacetanilide (17.7 g.), dissolved in ethanol (40 ml), was treated with ethanolic solution (50 ml) of benzoylhydrazine (15.0 g.) and a few drops of HCl (dil.) and stirred well. On keeping the solution for 24 hr., white, short needles separated. The product was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 171-73°, yield 80%.

Acetoacetanilide Salicylhydrazone.—Acetoacetanilide (17.7 g.), dissolved in ethanol (30 ml), was mixed with an ethanolic solution of salicylhydrazine (16 g. in 100 ml) and a few drops of HCl (dil.) in a beaker (250 ml). On stirring the mixture, the separation of the product in bulk started. After half an hour, the product was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 180°, yield 90%.

The semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones, benzoylhydrazones, and salicylhydrazones of the other amides of the series were prepared by following appropriate methods outlined above. The products obtained are white in colour; their m.p., analysis (micro), and molecular formulas are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

No.	Substance.	Acetoacetaryl amide semicarbazones.			Acetoacetaryl amide thiosemicarbazones.				
		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.	Formula	M.P.	% Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.		
1	A-anilide	100°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄	23.80	23.93	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ ON ₄ S ^s	101°	22.23	22.41
2	A- <i>o</i> -toluidide	174°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄	22.40	22.07	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S	154°	21.01	21.22
3	A- <i>p</i> -toluidide	171°	"	22.20	"	"	156°	21.00	"
4	A- <i>o</i> -chloroanilide	160°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	21.00	20.85	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON ₄ SCl	145°	19.90	19.60
5	A- <i>m</i> -chloroanilide	143°	"	20.75	"	"	151°	19.35	"
6	A- <i>p</i> -chloroanilide	175°	"	20.70	"	"	164°	19.60	"
7	A- <i>o</i> -anisidide	155°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄	21.50	21.22	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	150°	19.95	20.00
8	A- <i>p</i> -anisidide	165°	"	21.20	"	"	159°	20.02	"
9	A- <i>m</i> -xylylidide (2,4)	194°	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄	21.10	21.37	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ ON ₄ S	162°	20.30	20.15
10	A-2,5-dichloro-anilide	100°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	18.69	18.49	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ ON ₄ Cl ₂ S	103°	17.32	17.56
11	A-2,4-dimethoxy-anilide	176°	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄	19.30	19.05	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ S	153°	17.94	18.06
12	A- <i>p</i> -bromoanilide	188°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ Br	17.70	17.90	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON ₄ S	160°	16.80	17.03
13	A- <i>p</i> -phenotidide	162°	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₄	20.30	20.15	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ S	151°	10.20	19.05

A denotes acetacet.

3. Gingras et al., *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1960, 38, 712.

TABLE II

No.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
1	171-73°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	14.30	14.23	180°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	13.63	13.50
2	161°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	13.70	13.60	217°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	13.20	12.93
3	168°	"	13.75	"	177°	"	13.10	"
4	145°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	12.65	12.74	213°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	12.25	12.16
5	180°	"	12.80	"	196°	"	11.92	"
6	183°	"	12.91	"	192°	"	12.28	"
7	164°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	13.00	12.92	194°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃	12.00	12.25
8	171°	"	13.05	"	177°	"	12.30	"
9	156°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃	13.20	13.00	210°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	12.48	12.30
10	169°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	11.75	11.54	213°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	10.95	11.05
11	96°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃	11.78	11.83	179°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₃	11.50	11.32
12	185°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Br	11.10	11.23	199°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Br	10.60	10.77
13	172°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	12.50	12.40	179°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃	12.05	11.63

N.B. The number corresponds to the substituted amides in Table I.

All compounds, except acetacetanilide thiosemicarbazone³, recorded in the tables, are new products.

It is interesting to note that these substances during melting show meso-phase characteristic, especially smectic. A detailed study is in progress.

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